

Title: Blockchain for Infrastructure Agnostic Supply Chain and Tokenisation for Responsive Supply Chain

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INTRODUCTION:

Blockchain technology can serve to tie together broad diverse supply chains across organization regardless of database architecture yet with the commonality of security authorization and document authentication. In this way it will streamline the procurement and lifecycle tracking efficiency of tier 1, 2, 3 supply chains for organizations large and small. Tokenisation will serve as the "grease" providing customized incentive frameworks for more responsiveness and greater liquidity in blockchain-enabled modernized supply chains.

BIOGRAPHY:

[Bio on Jeremy Goodwin/CEO of SyncFab](#)

Jeremy is an international fintech executive fluent in Chinese and French and social impact entrepreneur passionate about technologies improving on the human condition including Additive and Advanced Manufacturing, AI (artificial intelligence), Bitcoin, Blockchain, Cleantech, Crypto, Decentralization, DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology), Ethereum and ML (Machine Learning).

Currently, Jeremy is CEO of SyncFab an IIoT Industry 4.0 Blockchain Manufacturing Industry Partner to the \$140MM US D.O.E. & D.O.C. Clean Energy Smart Manufacturing Innovation Initiative (CESMII) appointed by the White House and US Departments of Energy and Commerce National Network for Manufacturing Innovation (NNMI). SyncFab is also the San Francisco Mayor's Office of Civic Innovation - 2016 Startup in Residence (STIR) in partnership with the Cities of San Leandro, Oakland and West Sacramento.

From 2008 - 2012, Jeremy served as Executive President and CFO of China Advanced Construction Materials Company leading it to peak performance of 2,000 employees and NASDAQ IPO. As the only bilingual member of the company board of directors, he was responsible for negotiating large international contracts, implementing SOX 404 compliance, managing international accounting audits, SEC and shareholder communications. Jeremy successfully clinched a \$100M Private Equity investment offer in support of company expansion plans and NASDAQ listing before board decision to privatize.

From 2002 - 2008, Jeremy was Managing Director of 3G Capital Partners and Global Capital

Group - Trans-Pacific Merchant Banking Firms with more than \$250M in transactions. Mandates ranged from \$100M plant modernization for ShaGang Steel - China's 5th largest to a \$20MJV with NYSE Mueller Industries.

From 1996 - 2002, Jeremy worked as a financial executive at ING Barings, Baring Capital Partners, ABN Amro, Mees Pierson in New York, London, Amsterdam, Geneva, Beijing, Hong Kong in mandates including Carlyle Partners first \$1BN Fund.